

Chemical Examination of *Christisonia Bicolor* Gardn.

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The rare carotenoid, sazafrin, $C_{27}H_{38}O_4$, has been isolated from the rhizomes of *Christisonia bicolor* Gardn., a parasite on *Vitex negundo*. Its NMR and IR absorption spectra have been discussed.

Christisonia bicolor Gardn. (Family, Orobanchaceae) (Hindi: Nirgundi) is a root parasite on various species of plants, particularly on *Vitex negundo* Linn. It is found at an altitude of 3,000-4,000 feet in the Nilgiri Hills and in Madhya Pradesh, growing abundantly on the roots of infected plants in the winter season and protruding 3-6 inches above the soil. The herb is hairy, with very short, scaly, reddish brown stem and cylindrical, warted rhizome and bears yellow flowers¹.

The plant is used in the Ayurvedic system of medicine as a purgative and stimulant. It is frequently confused with its host, *Vitex negundo*, which is also sold under the name "nirgundi" and for the same medicinal purposes². A survey of the literature showed that no work had been done on *C. bicolor* and it was therefore considered of interest to undertake its systematic chemical investigation.

The material* employed was collected from the Banda district of Uttar Pradesh where it was found as a parasite on *Vitex negundo*. The ether extract of the powdered drug provided a crystalline, orange-red pigment, m.p. 209-210°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -114^\circ$ (ethanol), in 0.1% yield. The homogeneity of the pigment was established by paper chromatography and also by thin-layer chromatography on Kieselgel G.

The elementary analysis of the compound corresponded to the empirical formula $C_{26.87}H_{37.77}O$. It did not exhibit any colour with ferric chloride and tests for carbonyl, quinone, and methylenedioxy groups were negative. The compound did not contain a methoxyl group. It is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, but dissolves in dilute solutions of sodium carbonate and caustic soda from which it can be regenerated on acidification. The presence of a carboxyl group was established by formation of a methyl ester, m.p. 189°, insoluble in dilute alkali, which could be saponified to regenerate the original compound. The deep colour of the compound, its light absorption maxima at 428 and 458 μ as well as its colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric and hydrochloric acids and with antimony trichloride suggest that the pigment may be a carotenoid.

The IR spectrum (Fig. 1) of the methyl ester of the compound is very informative. Bands at 3509 cm^{-1} and 1672 cm^{-1} indicate presence of OH group and an ester, conjugated with a double bond, respectively. The doublet at 1379 cm^{-1} could be due to the deformation vibration (symmetrical mode) of two Me groups on the same carbon atom. The absence of free H atoms on this carbon is indicated by the single skeletal vibration at 1190 cm^{-1} .

1. Hooker, "Flora of British India", Vol. IV, p. 319.

2. Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Part III, 1939.

* Kindly identified by Dr. B. S. Trivedi of the Botany Department of this University and Dr. Pratap Singh of the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, to whom the authors' thanks are due.

The medium bands at 1058 and 1005 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the ring deformation vibration of a cyclohexane ring, whereas the strong absorption at 1600 cm^{-1} can be due to a system of conjugated double bonds.

FIG. 1. IR curve of methylazafrin in KBr pellet.

FIG. 2. NMR curve of methylazafrin using tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

The integration of the NMR spectrum (Fig. 2) of the methyl ester indicates the presence of forty protons based on the assumption that there is only one COOMe group. The spectrum further shows presence of six Me groups of which two are *gem* dimethyls (peaks at 8.85 and 9.157), one is an Me on a carbon atom carrying an electronegative group, such as,

OH (peak at 8.80 τ), whereas the remaining three Me groups are attached to ethylenic carbon atoms (8.01 and 8.08 τ). There are eleven ethylenic protons in the molecule.

The carotenoid nature of the pigment and presence of a carboxyl group in it, taken in conjunction with the physical and spectral data of the compound and of its methyl ester, suggest its identity with a known carotenoid, azafrin, $C_{22}H_{38}O_4$. This carotenoid is very rare and has been reported till now only from two species of *Escobedia*, *E. scabrifolia*³ and *E. linearis*⁴, both indigenous to South America where the red pigment is known as "azafran" or "azafranillo" and is used for colouring fats. The analytical data of our compound are in agreement with the molecular formula of azafrin and the identity of the two has been confirmed by the mixed m.p. determination of the ethyl ester of our compound with authentic ethylazafrin (authentic azafrin was not available) and the superimposability of their IR spectra.

Stereochemistry.—Azafrin has a terminal disubstituted double bond as shown by the two doublets at 2.62 and 4.15 τ in the NMR spectrum and since this is also a feature of the spectrum of all *trans*-bixin⁵, it is also likely that azafrin has a *trans* arrangement at the terminal double bond. The IR absorption at 968 cm^{-1} also indicates a disubstituted *trans*-ethylenic bond. The absence of a *cis*-C-CH=CH-C group is indicated by the lack of absorption at 778 cm^{-1} (12.84 μ)⁶.

The ethanolic extract of the plant appears to contain glycosides. Further work on their isolation is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

The rhizomes of *C. bicolor* were dried in the shade and finely powdered. The powder (10 kg.) was extracted successively with light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) and ether in a Soxhlet apparatus and then percolated with rectified spirit.

As the oily residue obtained on concentration of the light petroleum extract was negligible, it was not investigated further.

The ether extract was concentrated to a small volume and kept in the cold when an orange-red, crystalline solid was deposited (10 g.). This was filtered and crystallised from a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate (7:3) when needles, m.p. 204-205°, were obtained. This was further purified by chromatography on a column of silica gel, using benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) for development. The main red band was eluted with the same solvent and the residue from the eluate was recrystallised from benzene when the m.p. of the compound was raised to 209-10°. The pigment provided single spots on paper chromatography (Whatman No. 1 paper, pretreated with phosphate buffer, pH 7.5; solvent butanol⁷) and on thin-layer chromatography on Kieselgel G (solvent: benzene-chloroform, 1:1). [α]_D²⁰ -114° (c, 0.5; ethanol). [Found: C, 76.18; H, 9.03; OMe, 0.0; active H, 0.702; C-Me, 16.12. Calc.

3. Liebermann, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 850.

4. Takeda and Okta, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1939, 258, 6; Karrer and Jucker, "Carotenoids", 1950, p. 284.

5. Barber et al., *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 23.

6. Lunde and Zechmeister, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1947.

for $C_{27}H_{38}O_4$: C, 76.05; H, 8.92; active H (for three), 0.7 C-Me (for 5), 17.60%]. λ_{max} (in chloroform) at 428 and 458 $m\mu$.

Azafrin is insoluble in water and light petroleum; it is fairly soluble in ethyl acetate, pyridine, ethanol, benzene, and acetic acid, but very sparingly soluble in ether. It shows entirely hypophasic properties when partitioned between light petroleum and 90% methanol. It dissolves in dilute alkali and sodium carbonate solution and is regenerated on acidification.

The pigment dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with an intense blue colour which changed to brown on dilution with water. When it was dissolved in ether and the ethereal solution shaken with HCl (conc.), a blue colour was produced in the acid layer. On adding antimony trichloride in chloroform solution, azafrin developed a green colour, changing later to blue.

Methylazafrin.—Azafrin (400 mg.) and methyl iodide (1 ml) were refluxed for 12 hours in dry acetone (20 ml) over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The reaction mixture was filtered from the potassium carbonate and the solvent removed. The residue was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed on a column of alumina, using benzene as eluent. The eluate of the main red band was concentrated when orange-red, rhombic crystals were obtained, m.p. 189–90°. (Found: C, 76.29; H, 9.2. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{46}O_4$: C, 76.36; H, 9.09%). λ_{max} (in chloroform) at 428 and 458 $m\mu$. The IR. spectrum (Fig. 1) showed bands at 3509, 1672, 1379, 1190, 1058, 1005, 1600, 968, and 778 cm^{-1} .

Ethylazafrin was prepared in the usual manner by treatment of azafrin with diethyl sulphate and alkali, m.p. 182°. (Found: C, 76.53; H, 9.32. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{48}O_4$: C, 76.65; H, 9.25%). There was no depression in m.p. when admixed with an authentic sample of ethylazafrin.

Perhydroazafrin.—Azafrin (8 mg.) was hydrogenated in methanolic solution with platinum black as catalyst. The catalyst was filtered and the solvent removed when a colorless, viscous oil was obtained which distilled under high vacuum. [Found: Absorption of hydrogen at NTP, 2.86 ml. Calc. for $C_{27}H_{38}O_4$ (for 7 double bonds), 2.94 ml].

The authors' thanks are due to Prof. Richard Kuhn, Max Planck Institute, Heidelberg, Germany, for the supply of an authentic sample of methylazafrin and to Prof. L. M. Jackman, University of Melbourne, Australia, for the NMR spectrum. They also thank Dr. M. L. Dhar, Director, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for providing certain facilities and Dr. M.M. Dhar for valuable discussions. One of them (S.P.S.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the grant of a junior research fellowship.